

Rac-4i

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-172-RAC-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	22	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	xt 2 172 rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/31/2021 2:35:52 PM CST		
Date Processed:	11/29/2021 3:41:06 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.407	3451806	49.04	149455
2	18.406	3586285	50.96	83871

Asy-4i

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-173-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	23	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 2 173
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/31/2021 2:01:32 PM CST		
Date Processed:	11/29/2021 3:43:08 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.393	31126243	97.16	1387939
2	18.646	909667	2.84	19510